

The School Food Standards Compliance Pilot:

A Yorkshire Based Case Study

Acknowledgements

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Executive summary

Over the last two decades the number of children living with obesity in England has increased, to more than one in five, by the time children reach Year 6.

School meals provide the opportunity to address the dietary health of children on a population scale. However, compliance with the mandatory School Food Standards (SFS), which regulate the food to be provided to children at school, is not currently routinely monitored. Therefore, differences may exist between what food is mandated and what is offered to, and consumed by, children meaning that school food may not be optimised to influence dietary health.

The Food Standards Agency (FSA) and Department for Education (DfE) conducted a pilot study in 2022 – 2023 in which they explored whether Food Safety Officers (FSOs) could incorporate checks for potential non-compliance with SFS in their existing visits to schools and identify issues for follow up. The study concluded that FSOs could incorporate SFS compliance checks within their existing programme and that issues of non-compliance were able to be identified. However, it was noted by participants that the limited scope of the checks in this pilot, through the use of three rotating question sets, may not be sufficient to reflect compliance if the scheme was to be extended for this purpose.

This study explored the efficacy of the FSA compliance pilot test question sets to assess adherence to SFS applicable to lunch time servings, in the context of 18 menu cycles and 11 datasets of consumption in Yorkshire primary schools. The results revealed low compliance with all three of the pilot question sets, and inconsistency between the ease of passing between the three question sets. The results also identified low pass rates for questions related to starchy foods, dessert and oily fish. There were notable differences between choice and consumption, with vegetables being chosen frequently, but being consumed the least. In addition, menu compliance was not always an accurate reflection of consumption, for example fruit was consistently offered but not often chosen. There was also a difficulty establishing compliance from limited information on menus and without further detail on ingredients and preparation methods.

The question sets were intended to test the possibility of using FSOs to undertake compliance checks and therefore did not cover all areas of the SFS. Key areas such as milk, dairy and protein were not fully assessed during this pilot. The low overall compliance with SFS found in this study highlights the requirement for, and importance of, a formal system of independent monitoring. If the pilot were to be extended, with additional time for FSOs to undertake more comprehensive checks, the limitation of the restricted rotating question sets in the pilot could be addressed with a tiered format that utilises a set of essential questions, accompanied by supplementary questions, chosen by FSOs.

Further nutritional support for FSOs to establish and evaluate details on ingredients and preparation methods would likely improve the effectiveness of the checks. These changes may allow for a more comparable compliance monitoring process that focuses on current dietary challenges amongst children.

1. Introduction

In England, 12.4% of reception-aged children (4-5 years) are living with overweight and almost one in 10 are living with obesity (NHS England, 2024), with prevalence increasing to 13.8% and 22.1% for overweight and obesity respectively, by the end of Year 6 (NHS England, 2024). Furthermore, severe obesity prevalence in Year 6 (5.5%) was more than double that of reception aged children (2.6%) (NHS England, 2024). This highlights the primary school years as a key opportunity for interventions which target excessive weight gain and childhood obesity onset.

Obesity in childhood often persists into adulthood, with approximately 80% of adolescents living with obesity still living with the condition as adults (Simmonds et al. 2016). Obesity is a leading risk factor for noncommunicable diseases, including type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease and certain cancers (World Health Organisation, 2025). Furthermore, poor diet has been linked to obesity and stress-related mental health conditions (Bremner et al. 2020) and an unhealthy diet early in life is associated with symptoms of anxiety and depression later in childhood (Vejrup et al. 2023), emphasising the importance of improving children's dietary quality early.

Obesity prevalence in Year 6 children has remained the same since 2010 (NHS England, 2024). This is despite the introduction of childhood obesity prevention strategies, such as the Childhood Obesity Plan (GOV.UK, 2019), which have been criticised for a lack of focus on the social determinants of childhood obesity (Griffin et al. 2021). Children's diets do not currently align with government recommendations (Office for Health Improvements and Disparities, 2025), with high intakes of free sugars and saturated fats, and inadequate consumption of fruits, vegetables and fibre (Office for Health Improvements and Disparities, 2025), suggesting that government policies may be failing to effectively account for the factors that drive childhood obesity in the UK.

The prevalence of obesity varies significantly across socioeconomic groups (Candio et al. 2023). Notably, Year 6 children in the most deprived areas experience obesity rates of more than twice those in the least deprived areas (NHS England, 2024). This highlights the disproportionate risk among socioeconomically disadvantaged families.

Nine million children attend school in England (Department for Education, 2025) where approximately 30% of their daily energy intake is consumed throughout the school day (Nathan et al. 2019). As promoting a healthy diet, dietary modification and increased physical activity is important to address childhood obesity (Leung et al. 2024), schools provide an opportune setting to reduce childhood obesity while also reducing food insecurity, providing school meals are of sufficient quality. School food interventions and policies have the potential to reach all children on an equal basis, including those at the highest risk of poor diet quality and obesity.

1. Introduction

The Requirements for School Food Regulations 2014 (Department for Education, 2014) in England, known as the School Food Standards (SFS) (GOV.UK, 2025), define which foods and drinks schools must provide, restrict or prohibit. They are categorised into standards that apply to school food provision at lunch, outside of lunch and throughout the entire school day. The SFS regulate the provision of food in six food groups, as follows: starchy foods; fruit and vegetables; milk and dairy; meat, fish, eggs, beans and other non-dairy protein; foods high in fat, sugar and salt; and healthy drinks.

The introduction of mandatory SFS has been linked to improved food provision and dietary intake in English schools (Adamson et al. 2013). However, a lack of external compliance monitoring is apparent in England (McIntyre et al. 2021, Murphy et al. 2024) despite concerns about the importance of this for implementation and overall impact of the SFS (Dimpleby et al. 2013). It has been suggested that the inability of previous government strategies to reduce obesity may be linked to failures of implementation and evaluation (Theis et al. 2021). Therefore, it is likely that clearer guidance, monitoring and evaluation could improve the effectiveness of SFS to influence diet quality (Adamson et al. 2013).

High levels of non-compliance to the SFS have been found in English secondary schools (Pallan et al. 2024), which is particularly important given the upcoming expansion of free school meal (FSM) provision to 500,000 additional children in England (GOV.UK, 2025). Increased universal FSM provision has been associated with reduced Body Mass Index (BMI) and obesity rates, particularly in primary school children (Holford et al. 2024), which emphasises the need for consistent, long-term evaluation and monitoring of SFS compliance to optimise the potential of the school meal system to improve child health.

To address the lack of monitoring of the SFS, the Food Standards Agency (FSA) and The Department for Education with support from the Office of Health Improvement and Disparities launched the School Food Standards Compliance Pilot (Food Standards Agency, 2024). The pilot was delivered in three phases: Discovery Phase, Feasibility Phase 1 and Feasibility Phase 2. This report primarily focuses on the pilot questions used in, and findings from, Feasibility Phase 2. The primary objectives of the pilot were:

1. To test if Food Safety Officers (FSOs) carrying out food hygiene inspections could ask questions, and make observations of food preparation or service areas, to identify instances of potential non-compliance with the SFS. This is referred to as the 'School Food Standards check' and
2. Where instances of potential non-compliance with the SFS were identified, if appropriate teams within local authorities were able to provide support to schools to make improvements.

1. Introduction

Feasibility Phase 2 introduced rotating question sets, an adaptation from Phase 1 to make the process easier and more efficient. This included suitability for checking by FSOs, who were not trained in nutrition, and the ability to complete the checks in less than 20 minutes. FSOs who administered the checks were asked to rotate the set used at each school they visited. There were three question sets used, each consisting of 3-4 questions: Set A, Set B and Set C. During the pilot, Set C was considered much easier to pass, which some local authorities believed reduced the quality of the checks. While there are 21 SFS applying to lunches, the pilot's question sets covered only 11. It is therefore important to consider which standards were included or omitted in the pilot and evaluate whether this provided a fair and representative measure of compliance.

Another key finding of Phase 2 was that many local authority participants believed changes to the question sets, based on Phase 1 feedback, and the rotation requirement, reduced data quality. For example, 8/18 FSOs noticed non-compliance beyond the question set they were evaluating, 7/17 FSOs found the rotating question sets made the checks worse and an additional 6/17 noted little improvement from Phase 1. Additionally, several FSOs noted that clarification was required on certain questions.

The ability of SFS to improve children's dietary quality is based on certain assumptions, including that schools comply with the requirements. Schools typically follow a two-to-three-week menu cycle that includes 'dishes of the day' which often form the basis for meeting the SFS due to the ability to include a variety of required food groups. In addition, 'grab-and-go' options are often available and have been shown in one study to be the most popular choices amongst pupils (Ensaff et al. 2013). Large discrepancies between theoretical menu cycles and real pupil choices are, therefore, likely to be possible (Ensaff et al. 2013, Gould et al. 2006). There is insufficient research on whether SFS compliant menus are reflective of what children consume. Studies investigating the association between SFS compliance and nutritional intake are conflicting, which may result from a discrepancy between school menus and food consumption (Murphy et al. 2024, Spence et al. 2014).

Understanding pupil choice and consumption patterns is essential for understanding nutritional intake and optimising any extension to the piloted compliance check process. Knowing what children choose and consume from the menu is likely to be as important, if not more so, than how closely school menus adhere to the SFS. This study predominantly explores whether the use of the FSA compliance pilot questions has the potential to present a comprehensive view of SFS compliance using a case study of Yorkshire primary schools. The research aims include:

1. To explore what menu (n=18) and consumption data (n=11) across Yorkshire primary schools reveal about the strengths and limitations of using a limited basis of the rotating question sets to check for non-compliance as used in the pilot.
2. To evaluate how consistently the SFS compliance might be assessed using the FSA Pilot non-compliance rotating question sets (A, B and C).
3. To identify potential areas for improvement in the implementation and monitoring of the SFS compliance and to contribute evidence that may support a more consistent, practical and effective compliance approach should the pilot be considered for a more extensive roll out in future.

2. Methods

2.1 Design

This was a mixed methods study combining menu cycle analysis in a sample of 18 Yorkshire primary schools with data from the direct observation of school lunches in 11 of those schools. The observation data was collected as part of the FixOurFood programme of work with ethical approval from the University of York (HSRGC/2021/466/D). The study was designed to assess compliance with the SFS of the school menus and in the context of the children's selection, consumption and waste of food served at lunch.

2.2 Sample and Recruitment

All state funded primary schools in Yorkshire (n=1,772) were eligible and invited to participate in the wider FixOurFood research programme including an observation day which collected data on what food was offered, and what children consumed, that day at lunch. Recruitment occurred over three years through engagement with school leaders, local authority leads, catering staff and school governors. A cohort of 25 schools were recruited to take part in the observation days. The sampling framework was designed to include a variety of schools with differing Free School Meal (FSM) eligibility, English as additional language percentage, urban or rural geographical location and school size. Analysis of the observation day data for all 25 schools was still ongoing at the time of this study, therefore menu data for 18 schools, alongside consumption data from 11 of the schools, were available and included in this study.

2.3 Data Collection

2.3.1 Theoretical Menu Cycle Data

Two-to-four-week lunch menu rotations were collected from the websites of 18 of the 25 primary schools in Yorkshire that had been selected for observation days. Schools were anonymised to maintain confidentiality and allocated an identifier (1-18). The collection dates were as close as possible to the observation day period, ranging from February 2022 to July 2025.

2.3.2 Observation Day Data

On observation days, portions of each food item being offered at lunch was weighed independently by two researchers using scales to measure the mass (g) and photographed to record the visual representation of that mass. All pupils' trays/plates were then photographed at the point of service and at the end of consumption. Each tray/plate was given a number to link pre- and post-meal photos, allowing calculation of food mass consumed (g) and food mass wasted (g). All observational data was anonymised to ensure it was not possible to link any photo to an individual pupil.

For each tray/plate, the following data were recorded: student number, key stage, foods selected, SFS group, mass of food served (g), composition of food served, total mass of meal (g), mass of food consumed (g) and mass of food wasted (g). Each school was allocated an anonymous identifier (1-11).

2. Methods

2.4. Data Analysis

2.4.1 Theoretical Menu Cycle Analysis

Each menu listed three to four daily lunch options, typically including two 'dishes of the day' (one vegetarian and/or halal) and a jacket potato or sandwich option, accompanied by a dessert. Vegetables and salad were stated to be served as accompaniments, offered as side options or stated as always available. Fruit was almost always (n=17) stated to be provided, either with dessert, as a second dessert option or listed as always available.

Eighteen menus were assessed against the SFS compliance pilot check questions. The three question sets; Set A, Set B and Set C, and their individual questions are listed in Table 1. Question Set B Q.1 and Q.2 were excluded from the assessment because they applied to school food provision outside of lunch and therefore could not be scored based on the school lunch menu. The data was analysed to show menu compliance for each school, between question sets and by individual question. Each question was scored on a pass or fail basis. It should be noted that without the ability to review ingredients and preparation methods it was sometimes difficult to establish whether items stated on the menus were compliant. For example potato wedges could be sliced potatoes simply baked in the oven, or they could be commercially pre-prepared or frozen versions which are usually flash fried in a factory and then baked on site. Therefore, assumptions were made where menus contained statements or implied practices as opposed to specific listings, and these are stated in Table 1. Information regarding what constitutes certain food groups (e.g., starchy food cooked in fat/oil) was collected from the school food standards practical guide (GOV.UK, 2025) or the FSA compliance pilot report (Food Standards Agency, 2024). Where necessary the notes of the researchers conducting the observation days were also consulted.

2. Methods

Table 1: SFS Pilot Compliance Questions and Scoring Criteria

Set and Questions	Criteria/Assumptions for Pass/Fail
<p>Set A Q1: Are one or more portions of fruit and one or more portions of vegetables provided every day at lunch?</p>	<p>Passed if both 'fruit/salad' was available daily was stated on the menu or if both fruit and veg was stated anywhere on the menu for each day.</p>
<p>Set A Q2: Are more than 2 portions of food which include pastry provided each week?</p>	<p>Failed if >2 portions listed per week.</p>
<p>Set A Q3: Is starchy food cooked in fat or oil provided on more than 2 days each week?</p>	<p>Based on definitions listed in pilot Phase 1 as including roast or sautéed potatoes; chips; potato wedges; pre-prepared potato products; fried rice, fried bread or fried noodles; hash browns; garlic bread; Yorkshire pudding; chapattis and naan made with fat; pancakes and waffles.</p>
<p>Set A Q4: Is oily fish provided at least once every three weeks at lunch?</p>	<p>Only salmon, sardines, and mackerel constituted oily fish, not tuna. Failed if stated 'fishcake' (presumed white fish). Passed if stated 'salmon fishcake'.</p>
<p>Set B Q1: Are snacks other than nuts, seeds, vegetables and fruit available?</p>	<p>Excluded as applied to school food provision outside of lunch.</p>
<p>Set B Q2: Are cakes, biscuits or desserts available outside of lunch?</p>	<p>Excluded as applied to school food provision outside of lunch.</p>
<p>Set B Q3: Is a meat or poultry product provided more often than permitted?</p>	<p>Meat and poultry products included sausages; burgers; scotch pies, bridies, sausage rolls, cornish pasty, encased meat pastry pies, cold pork pie; breaded or battered shaped chicken and turkey products, e.g. nuggets, goujons, burgers.</p>

2. Methods

Table 1: SFS Pilot Compliance Questions and Scoring Criteria

Set and Questions	Criteria/Assumptions for Pass/Fail
<p>Set B Q4: Is a portion of wholegrain starchy food provided at least once in the week at lunch?</p>	<p>Failed if wholegrain or 50/50 is not explicitly stated beside the starchy food product.</p>
<p>Set C Q1: Are confectionery, chocolate and chocolate coated products available?</p>	<p>'Confectionery' included chewing gum, cereal bars, processed fruit bars, non-chocolate confectionery (with/without sugar), chocolate in any form (except hot chocolate), any product containing or coated with chocolate and any chocolate-flavoured substance, but excludes cocoa powder used in cakes, biscuits and puddings. If 'chocolate' was stated this was assumed to use real chocolate.</p>
<p>Set C Q2: Are more than 2 portions of food that has been deep-fried, batter-coated or breadcrumb-coated provided each week?</p>	<p>Deep fried: included chips (including oven chips), potato waffles, hash browns, samosas, plantain chips, spring rolls, doughnuts, pakora and bhajis. Batter-coated: included chicken nuggets, fish fingers and onion rings.</p>
<p>Set C Q3: Are non-permitted drinks available?</p>	<p>Passed/failed based on observation day researcher notes stating that no other drinks aside from water were available.</p>

The three question sets used in the compliance pilot were not designed to cover all the SFS requirements. Therefore, an additional six questions that covered the remaining SFS requirements that were not included in the pilot question sets were added to this study. They were tested against the same menus (n=18) and scored on the same pass/fail basis. The additional questions and accordant SFS are listed in Table 2.

2. Methods

Table 2: Additional SFS Questions and Standards Applied

Question	Standard Applied
Q1. Are 3 or more different types of starchy food provided each week?	3 or more different starchy foods each week should be provided.
Q2. Is a dessert containing at least 50% fruit provided 2 or more times each week?	A dessert containing at least 50% fruit should be provided two or more times each week.
Q3. Is a portion of milk/dairy provided each day?	A portion of food from this group to be provided every day.
Q4. Is a portion of meat, fish, eggs, beans or other non-dairy protein provided every day?	A portion of food from this group should be provided every day.
Q5. Is a portion of meat/poultry provided 3+ days a week?	A portion of meat or poultry to be provided on 3 or more days each week.
Q6. Is a portion of non-dairy vegetarian protein provided 3+ days a week?	For vegetarians, a portion of non-dairy protein should be available on 3 or more days each week.

The percentage pass rate for each individual question (A1-4, B3-4, C1-3 plus additional questions 1-6) and for each pilot question set was calculated.

2. Methods

2.4.2 Observation Day Data Analysis

Food items served to children on the observation days were categorised into SFS relevant groups as follows: fruit, vegetables, milk and dairy, high fat, sugar and salt (HFSS), meat/poultry, starchy food, fish, starchy food cooked in fat/oil and meat substitutes. Fruit and vegetables, starchy food and starchy food cooked in fat/oil and meat/poultry and fish were separated to allow for comparison with the pilot questions.

For each SFS group, the total selection count, mean selection count, mean percentage selected, mean percentage consumed and mean percentage wasted was calculated, and compared across SFS groups. The selection count, mean percentage consumed and mean percentage wasted was also calculated for individual food items (e.g. apple) to allow for further insights.

The percentage of food consumed was calculated as the proportion of mass consumed (g) divided by the mass served (g), multiplied by 100.

$$\text{Mass Consumed (g) / Mass Served (g) x 100}$$

The percentage of food wasted was calculated as the proportion of mass wasted (g) divided by the mass served (g), multiplied by 100.

$$\text{Mass Wasted (g) / Mass Served (g) x 100}$$

Descriptive statistics were used to summarise menu compliance, food selection, consumption and waste.

All analysis was conducted using Microsoft Excel (Microsoft® Excel® for Microsoft 365 MSO Version 2405 Build 16.0.17628.20006) and IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 29.0.2.0 (20)).

It should be noted that several standards relate to the provision of an item over a period of time, for example meat or poultry provided 3 times per week or oily fish provided once every 3 weeks. Looking at isolated observation days may not accurately reflect actual compliance.

3. Results

3.1. Menu Compliance

According to the pass / fail criteria for this study, as detailed in Table 1, none of the 18 school menu cycles tested passed all three pilot question sets (A, B and C) and 88% of school menu cycles failed all three sets. One school menu cycle passed Set B, two school menu cycles passed Set C and no school menu cycle passed Set A. One of the Set C passes came from the school menu cycle that also passed Set B. Of the three question sets, the mean pass rate was highest for Set C (63%), followed by Set A (47%) and Set B (46%). Set C therefore appeared to be the easiest set to pass.

Figure 1: Pass Rate of Pilot Questions. Questions A1-4, B3-4 and C1-3. All values are expressed as a percentage of total schools passing each question (n=9). Green= set A, red= set B and purple= set C.

Pass rates varied widely between individual questions (Figure 1). The questions with the lowest pass rate were A3 'Is starchy food cooked in fat or oil provided on more than 2 days each week?' (6%), B4 'Is a portion of wholegrain starchy food provided at least once in the week at lunch?' (22%), C1 'Are confectionery, chocolate and chocolate coated products available?' (27%) and A4 'Is oily fish provided at least once every three weeks at lunch?' (33%). Questions A2 'Are more than 2 portions of food which include pastry provided each week?' (94%) and C3 'Are non-permitted drinks available?' (94%) had the highest pass rates. Across all sets, the most frequent number of questions passed was two, suggesting an even distribution of potential difficulty or compliance.

3. Results

3.1. Menu Compliance

Figure 2: Pass Rate of Additional SFS Questions. All values are expressed as a percentage (n=6).

Additional questions covering the remaining SFS, not included in the pilot, and with the exception of Q2, were more consistent and had higher overall pass rates (Figure 2). Within this group, Q2 'Is a dessert containing at least 50% fruit provided 2 or more times each week?' (22%) had a low pass rate. Importantly, Q3 (milk and dairy) and Q6 (meat substitutes) addressed SFS food groups not included in the pilot questions. Q3 'Is a portion of milk/dairy provided each day?' (61%) had the second lowest pass rate of these questions, with almost 40% of schools not compliant with this requirement.

3. Results

3.2 Consumption Data

The consumption and waste data from the school meals assessed on the observation days of the 11 schools tested are summarised at Figure 3.

Figure 3: Average Percentage of Food Consumed and Wasted by SFS Group Across Yorkshire Schools Tested (n=11).

The values presented are the mean percentage of food mass (g) consumed or wasted relative to the mass (g) served within each SFS food group. Green bars show average percentage consumed and red bars show average percentage wasted.

Consumption rates, representing the proportion of food mass consumed compared to the amount served within each SFS group varied. Higher consumption rates show that a greater percentage of that food offered was consumed, while lower rates show higher levels of that food was wasted. Vegetables had the lowest rate of consumption (56.47%), followed by fish (71.22%) and starchy food cooked in fat/oil (72.07%). Milk and dairy (88.24%) and meat/poultry (83.60%) and meat substitutes (82.20%) had the highest rates of consumption.

3. Results

3.2 Consumption Data

Figure 4: Average Selection of SFS Groups Across Yorkshire Schools (n=11).

For each food group and individual item, the selection count was calculated as the number of trays/plates on which that food appeared within each school (Figure 4). These values were then averaged across the eleven observation days (number of trays food group appeared on/ total number of trays). This measure reflects the popularity of foods offered, independent of how much was consumed or wasted.

The most frequently selected food groups were vegetables (153), starchy food (140), and HFSS (113). Fish (6), fruit (24) and meat substitutes (24) had the lowest average selection count across the observation days.

3. Results

3.2 Consumption Data

Figure 5: Average Percentage Consumed and Average Selection of SFS Groups Across Yorkshire Schools (n=11). Green= average % consumed, red= average selection count.

Figure 5 compares the average selection count to the consumption rate for the 11 school meals observed. Fish was available on 8 of the 11 of the observation days but the average selection count was relatively low at 6, and when chosen, the average consumption was relatively low (71.2%) compared to the other food groups, reaching a minimum of 20.5% in one school. Notably, no oily fish was available on any observation day tested. However, it should be noted that testing one day from a limited sample of 11 schools may not be an accurate representation of the general provision of oily fish once every three weeks as required by SFS. All fish consumed across the observation days was tuna, often with mayonnaise in a jacket potato or sandwich.

Meat substitutes were available on three of the 11 days, with an average selection count of 24, but had high consumption rates (82.2%) when chosen.

A photograph showing a school kitchen environment. On the left, a woman wearing a white chef's hat and a white uniform is looking down. On the right, two young people, a girl and a boy, both wearing white lab coats, are looking towards the left. The background shows other people in a bright, well-lit kitchen.

3. Results

3.2 Consumption Data

Fruit was offered in 10 of the 11 school meals observed at lunch time, nearly meeting SFS requirements. However, in some schools, only one or two pupils chose fruit out of approximately 100 pupils. The fruit consumed included whole apples, pears, bananas and oranges which had consumption rates ranging from 46% to 76%. The two instances where fruit was presented as a fruit salad or chopped showed a marked increase in consumption of 91% and 100%, respectively.

Starchy food cooked in fat or oil was served on 5 of the 11 observation days. Across the 11 observation days, starchy food cooked in fat/oil had an average selection count of 45.

3.3 Menu Compliance & Consumption

It should be noted that higher compliance does not necessarily translate into lower food waste or higher consumption. The school with the lowest number of pilot questions passed (ID 11,1 question) had the highest average consumption rate (88%) of all schools. This suggests that other factors may have a greater influence on consumption than formal compliance with SFS standards.

4. Discussion

4.1 Main Findings and Comparison with the Pilot and Other Studies

The findings of this study reinforce the need for robust compliance checking of the School Food Standards. None of the primary schools in the study were fully compliant with the SFS tested.

This would indicate overall low adherence to the standards across the Yorkshire primary schools reviewed, comprising 18 menu cycles, and 11 meal services observed. Sixteen school menu cycles failed all three question sets from the FSA compliance pilot. This is in line with previous research finding low levels of compliance with SFS in England (Pallan et al. 2024).

With respect to the pilot questions used by the FSA, issues highlighted in this study relate to the lack of full coverage of all relevant standards, with questions designed to test the feasibility of detecting non-compliance with limited time and nutritional knowledge. Therefore, only a few questions were reviewed in each school and the question sets did not include all standards. There was also a difference in pass rates for the sets. For example, Set C had the highest pass rate in this study, aligning with feedback from public health teams during the pilot who also noted perceptions of passing / failing the checks, for example: 'Question Set C was too easy, when schools got set C it felt like they still might be non-compliant even when they passed' (Food Standards Agency, 2024). This included concerns from pilot participants about fairness between sets and questions over the reasons why some sets had higher pass rates. This could relate to many factors such as the difficulty, or cost, of providing certain items, or perceived child preferences, and further research is needed to understand the factors that influence compliance.

An important finding from the feedback of FSOs in the pilot study was that they found several questions confusing, particularly:

- Is starchy food cooked in fat or oil provided on more than 2 days a week?
- Is a meat or poultry product provided more often than permitted?
- Are more than 2 portions of food that has been deep-fried, batter-coated or breadcrumb coated provided each week?

4. Discussion

4.1 Main Findings and Comparison with the Pilot and Other Studies

Several FSOs had requested clarification on these questions and were still awaiting responses from the DfE at the time of publication (Food Standards Agency, 2024). This aligns with findings from the present study, where some questions were difficult to assess using the menu alone. Contributing factors included uncertainty about what foods the questions included, a lack of ingredient detail provided on the menus, and a lack of clarity on how certain foods are prepared (i.e. commercially processed, cooked in fat/oil, deep fried, etc.). Although Phase 1 of the pilot provides some guidance on these categories, it may be unclear to FSOs where to look for the relevant information and whether they have the nutritional knowledge to interpret this information. In practice, accurate assessment would likely require further discussions with the catering staff, and a review of the product ingredients and preparation methods, and the availability of support or clarification from the DfE or relevant public health department. This would likely add extra time and additional effort to the compliance checks. A key objective of introducing the rotating question sets was to shorten the duration of the checks, however, the difficulty interpreting compliance with the questions, and a lack of clear lines of support noted by the pilot participants may negate this effort.

Consistent with pilot findings, the question “Is a meat or poultry product provided more often than permitted?” was perceived as particularly problematic to answer, with confusion over whether this related to meat and poultry or a processed version. The meaning of ‘meat/poultry product’ becomes clearer upon further examination of the standards:

- Portion of meat or poultry on 3 or more days each week
- A meat or poultry product (manufactured or homemade, and meeting the legal requirements) no more than once each week in primary schools and twice each week in secondary schools (applies across the whole school day)

Revising the wording of this question to explicitly define the term within the context of compliance checks and differentiate between primary and secondary schools, in terms of their separate meat and poultry requirements, would likely improve accuracy, speed up check duration, and reduce FSO workload.

To further reduce check durations, some FSOs interviewed in the pilot recommended reviewing menus available on school websites prior to visits, as was undertaken in this study. However, as noted above, menus often lacked sufficient detail, for example, regarding fruit and vegetable provision and ingredients/preparation methods, requiring further investigation by FSOs. In this study, data collected by researchers on observation days supplemented information not provided on the menus (e.g. drinks provided at lunch). While pre-review of menus may present a useful strategy for preparation prior to the visit, used in isolation it may compromise accuracy due to incomplete or unclear information and the potential for differences between food on the menu and food served on the day. In addition, reviewing food served on an isolated day may not accurately reflect compliance. For example, in this study oily fish was not served on any of the days observed, this may be because it only needs to be served once every 3 weeks.

4. Discussion

4.1 Main Findings and Comparison with the Pilot and Other Studies

The pass rate of the individual questions varied considerably, with the number of schools passing each question ranging from 1 out of 18 to 17 out of 18.

The observation day data highlighted that starchy foods account for a substantial proportion of children's school meals, and were the most frequently selected food group across the observation days, averaging 185 selections per day and a high consumption rate of approximately 72%. Question A3, covering starchy food cooked in fat or oil, is therefore important to include, despite being challenging to assess. It had a low pass rate (6%) and was served on 5 of the 11 observation days, which likely exceeds the SFS limit of 2 days a week. Items provided included chips, roast potatoes and Yorkshire puddings. The other pilot question relating to starchy foods, 'Is a portion of wholegrain starchy food provided at least once in the week at lunch?', also had a low pass rate (22%). This is reinforced by the additional (non-pilot) Q1, 'Are 3 or more different types of starchy food provided each week?' which showed high compliance (83%). Therefore, suggesting that there may be an issue with the nutritional quality of the starchy foods being served rather than the frequency of provision, and highlighting the importance of ensuring that checks are undertaken by those with adequate knowledge of nutrition and food processing. To improve compliance with the SFS, efforts could prioritise increasing the availability of wholegrain starchy foods and reducing the frequency of those cooked in fat/oil. Wholegrain varieties of starchy foods are important sources of fibre and have been associated with a lower risk of certain cancers and type 2 diabetes (Scientific Advisory Committee on Nutrition, 2015). However, 96% of children aged 11-18 do not meet UK government fibre recommendations (Office for Health Improvements and Disparities, 2025) highlighting the importance of including these questions in the checks.

Question C1

'Are confectionery, chocolate and chocolate coated products available?' indicated low compliance (27%) with this standard across primary schools, aligning with findings from a previous study showing low compliance (26%) across secondary schools with standards restricting high fat, sugar and energy-dense foods (Pallan et al. 2024). Recent data (Office for Health Improvements and Disparities, 2025) shows that less than one in 10 children are meeting their recommended free sugars intake, therefore regulating the amount of HFSS food provided in schools is important. Previous research has shown that children who have school lunch consume, on average, 11g less total sugar across the school day than children who eat packed lunch (Evans et al. 2015), suggesting that school lunches do have the potential to reduce children's sugar intake.

4. Discussion

4.1 Main Findings and Comparison with the Pilot and Other Studies

Question A4

This looked at oily fish provision. No oily fish was available at any of the eleven observation days in this study, the only fish product available on any of the days was tuna. Furthermore, the only oily fish listed on any of the menu cycles reviewed was salmon, which was only present on one third of the menus. Research using NDNS data found that fish intake is low with approximately 4.7% of UK children meeting the fish, and 4.5% meeting the oily fish, recommendations (Kranz et al. 2017), and acceptability of oily fish is generally low amongst children (BDA, 2020). This may lead to school meal caterers limiting oily fish provision to avoid food waste (BDA, 2020). The British Dietetic Association recommend that the integration of pupil feedback and experimentation of how oily fish can be integrated into school lunches could help rectify this (BDA, 2020), furthermore, a German study indicated that even small amounts of oily fish consumption is enough to significantly improve children's omega-3 intake compared to non-consumers (Tran et al. 2013). Therefore, despite the difficulties, compliance with this standard is important to measure, alongside a multifaceted approach to minimise food waste, and increase children's omega-3 fatty acid intake.

Question A1

NDNS data (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2025) shows that fewer than one in 10 children aged 11-18 meet the '5 A Day' fruit and vegetable recommendation. In this study, pilot question A1 'Are one or more portions of fruit and one or more portions of vegetables provided every day at lunch?' had a relatively low pass rate of 55%, which was likely because fruit was not listed as available. Fruit, when considered as a separate SFS group, had one of the lowest average selection counts across observation days (24) and one of the lowest consumption rates (72%), relative to other groups. In some schools, only one or two pupils chose fruit out of approximately 100, indicating that children may require encouragement from school staff to choose fruit. Previous research similarly reports that two-thirds of primary school-aged children did not consume any fruit at lunchtime (Upton et al. 2012). In the present study, this was particularly apparent with whole fruits, such as apples and oranges, with consumption rates ranging from 46% to 76%. In contrast, chopped fruits and fruit salads had higher consumption rates ranging from 91-100%. Therefore, children may be more inclined to eat fruit when incorporated into desserts or served in more appealing formats, such as chopped fruit or fruit salads. This is in line with recommendations from the World Health Organisation (2022) to incorporate appealing ways to encourage healthier choices by children. Therefore, including Question 2. 'Is a dessert containing at least 50% fruit provided 2 or more times each week?' in the pilot may help to ensure that compliance more accurately reflects actual consumption and increase fruit provision and consumption in primary schools.

4. Discussion

4.1 Main Findings and Comparison with the Pilot and Other Studies

Additional Question 3

Notably, no questions regarding milk and dairy were included in the pilot, despite dairy foods being an important source of energy, protein, calcium and vitamin A (GOV.UK, 2024).

NDNS data shows that most primary-aged children currently meet the recommended intakes of vitamin A and calcium, however, since 2008 there has been a 23% decline in vitamin A intakes among children aged 4-10 (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2025). In this study, dairy products had an average selection count of 43 and an average consumption rate of 83% across observation days, indicating that dairy contributes considerably to children's lunchtime diets. However, it is important to note that dairy products most frequently consumed on the observation days were yoghurt and cheese. While yoghurts contribute valuable nutrients, they have also been identified as a notable source of free sugars, accounting for 5.5% of intake in 4–10-year-olds (Williams et al., 2015). Although sugar content in yoghurts has declined by around 13% since 2016, many contain high levels of sugar and may not represent a healthy choice (Moore et al. 2020). Conversely, increased yoghurt consumption has been associated with improved overall dietary quality in UK children (Zhu et al., 2021).

Overall, the inclusion of a question that checks SFS compliance for dairy is warranted but monitoring of product type and quality (low fat and low sugar) could be of greater importance than simply tracking provision. Refining the wording to put a greater focus on quality may better align with improving dietary quality alongside understanding actual pupil consumption. In addition, a question focusing on the standard 'lower fat milk must be available for drinking at least once a day during school hours' is also relevant to this SFS group.

Milk is associated with nutritional benefit to primary-aged children (Rumbold et al. 2022). If limiting the number of questions for FSOs is important, enquiring about milk may replace Set C Q.3. 'Are non-permitted drinks available?' which had a 94% compliance rate across the eighteen schools, which was also reflected by the observation day data. However, it is important to consider the nuances of milk provision with flavoured milks containing added sugars and flavours noted as available during the observation days.

4. Discussion

4.1 Main Findings and Comparison with the Pilot and Other Studies

Other Additional Questions

The additional non-pilot questions not previously discussed covered meat, poultry, additional protein and non-dairy vegetarian protein and had relatively high pass rates ranging from 66-83%.

Foods within this group provide key nutrients including protein, iron and zinc (GOV.UK, 2024) and higher protein intake in mid-childhood has been associated with healthier body composition (Jen et al. 2018).

Iron intake remains a concern among school-aged children, 30% of 11–18-year-olds consume less than the lower reference nutrient intake (LRNI) for iron (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2025). Teenage girls are disproportionately affected, 9% of 11-18-year-old girls show blood markers for anaemia (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2025) and intakes of iron and zinc among females aged 11–14 years are significantly lower in the lowest-income groups compared with the highest (Thomas et al. 2022). This highlights a potential justification for including an additional question covering this SFS group, such as 'Is a portion of meat, fish, eggs, beans or other non-dairy protein provided every day?' despite having a high pass rate in this study.

Although current red and processed meat consumption is above the recommended 70g per day across all age groups (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2025), the existing question for this SFS group 'Is a meat or poultry product provided more often than permitted?' remains important to include due to the associated cancer risk (CRUK, 2019) and the relatively low pass rate (61%) observed in this study.

Despite vegetables being highly selected across school meals (average 153 selections per school), and menus largely complying with the standard of providing a portion of vegetables daily at lunch, the consumption rates of vegetables were low (56.47%). Consistent with this study, previous research indicates that while the proportion of children consuming any vegetables at lunchtime is more than double that consuming fruit, overall intake remains below recommended portions (Upton et al. 2012).

Despite being important to include in the pilot, theoretical compliance to this standard is not reflected by consumption data and does not necessarily translate into tangible improvements in children's fruit and vegetable consumption.

In addition to compliance monitoring, targeted interventions may be beneficial, for example, a three-year school-based program in Croatia combining workshops, homework, and pupil and parental education led to significant increases in fruit and vegetable intake in 89% of participating children (Ilic et al. 2022).

4. Discussion

4.2 Limitations

It should be noted that some pilot questions which related to the provision of food outside of the school lunch were not able to be evaluated through the data collected in this study.

For example, Set B Q1: 'Are snacks other than nuts, seeds, vegetables and fruit available?' and Set B Q2: 'Are cakes, biscuits or desserts available outside of lunch?' Therefore, the comparison of question sets did not include all relevant information. Future research should assess compliance with the FSA compliance pilot questions throughout the entire school day; however, this would likely require school visits that span the full school day alongside further questioning with school staff.

Similarly, it was not possible to assess whether certain food groups were provided using one day of observation data. For example, there may be discrepancies between menus and the food served, and foods such as meat or poultry may have been provided more often than permitted, though it was not possible to assess this based on consumption data from one day.

Another limitation is the relatively small sample size in this study. The observation day menu data covered 11 Yorkshire schools. This is likely to restrict the generalisability of the findings to schools across England, particularly as dietary behaviours and catering practices may vary regionally and between schools. Furthermore, the number of schools analysed for menu cycle compliance (n=18) did not align with the number included in the observation study, limiting the comparability between these two aspects of the analysis. These discrepancies are likely to reduce the strength of inferences drawn when comparing compliance data with observed consumption patterns.

Most menus on school websites did not include detail on ingredients or preparation methods requiring assumptions to be made. Whilst this subjective interpretation of compliance likely reflects that of the FSOs in the pilot, this may have led to errors in judging compliance in both circumstances. In addition, the menu cycles used for compliance assessment may not have been the same as those in operation on the observation days, which likely limits the accuracy of the comparison of the compliance and consumption data.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Overall compliance with the School Food Standards was low across the menu cycles of the 18 Yorkshire primary schools in this study. The FSA and DfE Compliance Pilot Feasibility Phase 2 question sets were rarely passed, with 16 of 18 schools failing all sets. Set C had the highest pass rate, consistent with findings from the pilot.

Assessing compliance based on school menus alone was found to be of limited use. Menus can be used as a preparation to help reduce the time needed on site for checks, but compliance assessment requires discussion with school staff and a clear understanding of ingredients and preparation methods, particularly for standards regulating items such as starchy foods cooked in fats or oils.

If using FSOs to identify non-compliance with SFS is to be rolled out beyond the pilot the compliance checks may benefit from the current question sets being revised and expanded to add clarity and cover all of the SFS. A tiered approach could improve comparability, with a core set of essential questions supported by current dietary and nutritional data, supplemented by additional questions chosen by FSOs to reflect local challenges. The issues identified in this study suggests that to optimise the compliance checks for the nutritional quality of school meals, the most useful core questions likely include:

Set A

Q1: Are one or more portions of fruit and one or more portions of vegetables provided every day at lunch?

Q3: Is starchy food cooked in fat or oil provided on more than 2 days each week?

Q4: Is oily fish provided at least once every three weeks at lunch?

Set B

Q3: Is a meat or poultry product provided more often than permitted?

Q4: Is a portion of wholegrain starchy food provided at least once a week at lunch?

Set C

Q1: Are confectionery, chocolate and chocolate coated products available?

Given the feedback from the pilot participants this is likely to require additional time and support for FSOs. In addition, the limited consumption data reviewed suggests that assessing compliance to these standards may not be enough to make a positive difference to school children's diets on their own. Additional strategies to promote consumption of these food groups should be considered and is a point for future research.

Overall the findings reinforce the need for a robust system of compliance checks. Both the pilot and this study suggest that whilst the FSOs could have a valuable role to play in compliance checking they likely require more support, and potentially more time, to determine compliance accurately. This includes guidance on ingredients, preparation methods and portioning. The results may also inform updates to the school food standards, providing clearer guidance on food categories and practical examples to improve implementation and compliance across schools.

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